

Efficient finite element modelling of litz wires in toroidal inductors

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Abstract

Accurate understanding of losses and frequency-dependent winding parameters have been an important aspect for selecting the right configuration of stranded conductors in power-electronic inductors. An approach for modelling frequency-dependent parameters of a winding with twisted wire bundles in toroidal inductors using a multi-axial sliced finite element (FE) modelling approach is presented here. A 2D magnetodynamic FE problem is solved in several axial and radial slices of the inductor, accounting for the twisted conductor bundles by varying the conductor positions in the slices. Case studies are presented for different levels and pitch lengths of twisting. The approach is validated against 3D FE simulations in the case of 3–4 parallel strands and against measurements in the case of 75, 105 and 125 strands, which would be impossibly heavy for conventional 3D FE tools. The results provide insight into the effect of strand grouping, twisting levels and twisting pitch on the frequency-dependent resistance of windings.

1 | INTRODUCTION

The exponential growth of power electronic systems after the mid-20th century has increased the usage of litz wire in magnetic components. They have been a proven solution for reducing eddy current losses due to frequency dependent effects up to a certain range of operational frequencies. The selection of the number of strands and their diameter has huge impact on total proximity effect loss of the litz wire [1].

Litz wires consist of multiple strands twisted or bundles of strands which are twisted together. Figure 1 shows one possible construction with recursive twisting configurations, which can have multiple levels of twisting. Each level is twisted with a certain angle per unit length in the longitudinal direction of the wire. It has been observed that due to such structure, litz wires tend to unify the current sharing among the strands and hence, the frequency dependent power losses are reduced [2, 3]. However, this happens only up to a specific frequency, after which considerable losses are observed due to the circulating current [4] and the inter-bundle proximity effect [5, 6]. The twisting imperfections and inappropriate twisting pitch (length of lay in longitudinal direction of wire bundle) can produce a drastic rise in winding resistance and losses [7]. Hence, a comprehensive understanding of the frequency dependent phenomenon in litz wire is a key to the optimal design of magnetic components

[8, 9]. However, engineers face difficulties in accurately defining winding resistance for complex winding structures as a function of frequency during the optimization stage of magnetic components [10].

Analytical expressions, which are very handy for engineers because of their quick solutions, still have their limitations in accounting for different loss mechanisms when it comes to litz wires [11]. Many aspects like the number of strands and their diameter along with the twisting scheme and pitch come into play while designing inductor windings with litz wire. The internal structure of the litz wire affects the accuracy of AC resistance calculation for a wire bundle in the mid-range of frequencies below 500 kHz [12]. More importantly, due to the presence of airgaps and insulation between the strands, the conductivity of litz wire seen at the cross section is not homogenous which poses problems for analytical approaches [8].

To envisage the impact of frequency dependent phenomena in the design of the complex litz wire winding structure, the use of 3D finite element (FE) method (FEM) becomes necessary [11]. However, discretizing filamentary structures like litz wire strands in 3D will result into an extremely heavy computational problem. It may even be impossible to compute such a problem considering the computational cost and time. To tackle this problem, FEM homogenization techniques have been used with a 3D approach in [13–15]. In [16], an integral formulation

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FIGURE 1 Illustration of three different types of litz wires (denoted L1, L2 and L3)

approach for litz wire along with homogenization-based FEM is proposed. Such homogenization-based models exclude the effects of the stranded structure of the conductor and details of the field distribution inside the cross section of the bundles. It is also not possible to extract details of the eddy currents within individual strands with homogenization techniques. Such details are important for the manufacturability and the cost of litz wire. Hence, accurate knowledge of the loss behaviour under complex twisting is one of the important objectives for correct litz wire selection [17, 18].

An integral formulation based partial element equivalent circuit approach has been proposed in [12, 17, 19]. These methodologies still need support of FEM approach for successful analysis of litz wire windings in magnetic components where cores are involved. Hence, a stand-alone numerical approach for modelling inductors with the effect of core on the winding needs further treatment. To address the problems of 3D nature of the litz wire windings, a homogenization approach based on analytical formulation for complex permeability of winding conductor domains has been proposed in [20]. The complexly twisted litz wire winding still cannot be precisely modelled with the homogenized definitions of electric and magnetic properties in conducting and magnetising domains. In [21], an analytical approach is proposed to incur the complexity of a litz wire structure with multiple level of twisting. However, the magnetic core is excluded in the proposed method. Additionally, it has limitations on the minimum number of strands at the lowest twisting level and the maximum number of bundles at the highest level of twisting. Pure FE models capable of accounting for the 3D behaviour of the electromagnetic field in litz wire wound magnetic components with cores have not been presented so far. This article demonstrates the possibility to compute winding losses by considering a complex 3D nature of twisted conductor bundles in a toroidal inductor (Figure 2). This is achieved by coupling together 2D slices in axial and radial directions from the inductor as shown in Figure 3.

In this study, the toroidal inductors with equally distributed windings are analysed (Figure 2) for different litz wire configurations and twisting pitches. The work utilizes a multi-axial sliced FE model (MASM) for the analysis in MATLAB environment [22]. Initially, two simplified windings with three and four parallel strands are analysed and validated against 3D simulation

FIGURE 2 The simulated approximate sector 3D model for 3×0.6 mm and 4×0.52 mm cases

FIGURE 3 Approximation of one symmetry sector of a toroidal inductor by taking slices in axial and radial directions

results from COMSOL Multiphysics. Later, realistic cases with a higher number of strands are considered. Due to the limitations of computational resources, 3D FEM was not possible for the cases with higher number of strands and hence, experimental validations were carried out for those cases. The definitions of skin and proximity effects are adopted from [8, 23].

From here, the article is divided into three sections. Section 2 describes the methodology along with the details of the studied geometry, material, and model. The section also defines necessary terminologies used in this article. The computational and the experimental results are presented and discussed in Section 3. Section 4 provides conclusions about the presented research.

2 | METHODS

2.1 | Inductor and winding wire configurations

In this article, one-, two- and three-level litz wires (L1, L2, L3) are considered as shown in Figure 1. The following notations are used to denote the wire bundles:

- A bundle of strands is called an L1 wire.
- A bundle of L1 wires is called an L2 wire.
- A bundle of L2 wires is called an L3 wire.

TABLE 1 Studied twisting schemes in the toroidal inductor

Number of strands	Twisting levels	Configuration	Number of turns	DC resistance of winding (Ω)	Core
3	L1	3×0.6 mm	50	0.058	Air
4	L1	4×0.52 mm	50	0.058	Air
105	L2	$7 \times 15 \times 0.2$ mm	50	0.023	Air
75	L2	$3 \times 25 \times 0.2$ mm	50	0.032	Air
125	L1	125×0.1 mm	40	0.038	Air and SMC
125	L2	$5 \times 25 \times 0.1$ mm	40	0.039	Air and SMC
125	L3	$5 \times 5 \times 5 \times 0.1$ mm	40	0.040	Air and SMC

The arrangement of the strands in the wires is denoted as:

- $m_1 \times d$ for an L1 wire
- $m_2 \times m_1 \times d$ for an L2 wire
- $m_3 \times m_2 \times m_1 \times d$ for an L3 wire,

where m_1 is the number of strands in an L1 wire, m_2 is the number of L1 wires in an L2 wire, m_3 is the number of L2 wires in an L3 wire, and d is the strand diameter. For convenience, we denote $m_2 = m_3 = 1$ for an L1 wire and $m_3 = 1$ for an L2 wire. The total number of strands in the wire is then obtained as $m = m_1 m_2 m_3$.

The wire configurations studied in this article are shown in Table 1. All wires consider azimuthal twisting directions with respect to the longitudinal axis of the wire. The 125×0.1 mm wire was studied with three commonly used twisting schemes defined in [2], while the 105×0.2 mm and 75×0.2 mm wires have a twisting configuration similar to the cases studied in [8]. All litz wires with 125×0.1 mm category as well as the 75×0.2 mm wire are constructed manually in the laboratory. They are constructed recursively using a mechanical rotating hook arrangement, which is based on the idea of a rope making mechanism. The 105×0.2 mm wire was procured from Rudolf Pack litz.

As seen in Figure 1, the twisting topology in the model is defined such that an L3 twisted wire follows a circular twisting pattern in longitudinal direction. The L2 wire follows the smooth helical trajectory formed by L3 and the strand in L1 follows the resultant path produced by twisting of the L2 and L3 wires.

The MASM (in Figure 3) and 3D models (in Figure 2) are built for a single symmetry sector, that is, the region covered by one turn in an inductor with an evenly distributed winding. Four slices in radial (r constant) and axial (z constant) directions are considered in the MASM computations. The inner and outer radii of the core are denoted r_{in} and r_{out} , respectively. The height of the core is b and the cases with $N = 50$ and $N = 40$ turns are considered. The turns are equally distributed over the periphery of core as shown in Figure 2. The symmetry sector covers an angle of $\varphi_{\text{sym}} = 2\pi/N$. The strands in L1, L2, and L3 wires are spatially placed based on the decided twisting angles per unit length ϑ_1 , ϑ_2 , and ϑ_3 calculated from

the respective pitch lengths of the twisting levels. A parameterized model is developed for defining the wire structures with multi-level twisting. The conductor cross sections are approximated as circular sections in the slice planes. The current density in the slice plane is assumed to be perpendicular to the plane.

The inter-slice positions of the strands in such geometries can be defined by the Frenet–Serret frame [11]. However, a simpler geometrical approach is adopted here which partly makes the strands follow the Frenet–Serret frame. The approach is defined using the following entities: The conductor strand is indexed as j . The slices in both axial and radial directions are indexed with k . τ_1 , τ_2 and τ_3 are the twist pitch lengths for the L1, L2, and L3 wires, respectively. Hence, the twist angles in each slice are formulated as:

$$\begin{cases} \vartheta_{k,1} = l_k \cdot (2\pi/\tau_1) \\ \vartheta_{k,2} = l_k \cdot (2\pi/\tau_2) \\ \vartheta_{k,3} = l_k \cdot (2\pi/\tau_3) \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where l_k is the distance along the conductor between slice k and the starting point of the turn which is chosen to be located at the inner side and vertically in the middle of the toroid as shown in Figure 4. l_k^+ and l_k^- represent the distance of the positive and the negative coil sides in slice k from the starting point. The positions of the conductor strands can then be calculated by:

$$\begin{aligned} x_{k,j} = & R_1 \cdot \cos(\varphi_{j,1} + \vartheta_{k,1}) \\ & + R_2 \cdot \cos(\varphi_{j,2} + \vartheta_{k,2}) + R_3 \cdot \cos(\varphi_{j,3} + \vartheta_{k,3}) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

$$\begin{aligned} y_{k,j} = & R_1 \cdot \sin(\varphi_{j,1} + \vartheta_{k,1}) \\ & + R_2 \cdot \sin(\varphi_{j,2} + \vartheta_{k,2}) + R_3 \cdot \sin(\varphi_{j,3} + \vartheta_{k,3}) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where R_1 , R_2 and R_3 are the radii of the twisting trajectories at each level seen at the cross section of wire. φ_1 , φ_2 and φ_3 are the relative angular positions of a strand in the L1, L2, and L3 wires. The obtained x and y positions are then transferred to the cylindrical coordinate system in MASM model.

FIGURE 4 Illustration of the wire distance seen at the slice from the starting point

2.2 | Material definitions

The paper focuses on providing the approach of modelling windings with twisted wire bundles. Hence, initial computations are carried out by excluding the effect of core. This is done by setting the permeability of the core regions to that of free space (μ_0). Similar computations are later performed for the inductors with soft magnetic composite (SMC) core material to study the effect of the core on the AC winding resistance. Kool M μ core material with relative permeability $\mu_r = 125$ from Magnetics Inc. is considered here for the study [24]. The complex reluctivity of the SMC material is determined as a function of the frequency as follows. The core loss density in the material catalogue of the manufacturer is defined for sinusoidally varying flux density with frequency f and amplitude B as:

$$p = \alpha \left(\frac{f}{\text{kHz}} \right)^\beta \left(\frac{2B}{\text{T}} \right)^\gamma \quad (4)$$

where $\alpha = 44.3 \text{ mW/cm}^3$, $\beta = 1.541$, and $\gamma = 1.988$. On the other hand, the core loss density can be written in terms of the imaginary part of the reluctivity ν_{im} as:

$$p = \pi f \nu_{\text{im}} B^2 \quad (5)$$

Combining Equations (4) and (5) yields:

$$\nu_{\text{im}} = \frac{2\alpha \left(\frac{f}{\text{kHz}} \right)^\beta \left(\frac{2B}{\text{T}} \right)^\gamma}{2\pi f B^2} \approx \frac{4}{\pi} \frac{\alpha}{\text{T}^2 \text{kHz}^\beta} f^{\beta-1} \quad (6)$$

where $\gamma \approx 2$ has been assumed.

To find the real and imaginary parts of the reluctivity for the considered SMC toroids, we define:

$$\nu_{\text{re}} = \frac{1}{\eta_1 \mu_r \mu_0} \quad (7)$$

$$\nu_{\text{im}} = \frac{4}{\pi} \frac{\eta_2 \alpha}{\text{T}^2 \text{kHz} \eta_3 \beta} f^{\eta_3 \beta - 1} \quad (8)$$

where η_1 , η_2 , and η_3 are coefficients fitted against impedance measurements from the SMC inductor wound with an L1 wire.

2.3 | Magnetic field equations for MASM

A 2D time-harmonic electromagnetic problem is defined using the AVI formulation [4, 25] in each slice k . The current of each conductor branch is coupled to the out-of-plane components of the magnetic vector potentials of the slices as well as the potential differences acting over the conductor regions in each slice. The complete system is given by:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{S} + j\omega\mathbf{T} & \mathbf{D}_\Omega & \mathbf{D}_\Gamma \\ j\omega\mathbf{C}_\Omega & -\mathbf{I} & \mathbf{R}\mathbf{M} \\ j\omega\mathbf{C}_\Gamma & \mathbf{M}^T & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{a} \\ \mathbf{u} \\ \mathbf{i} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{U} \end{bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

where $\mathbf{a} = [\mathbf{a}_1^T \dots \mathbf{a}_n^T]^T$ and $\mathbf{u} = [\mathbf{u}_1^T \dots \mathbf{u}_n^T]^T$ contain the nodal values of the vector potentials and the potential differences over the conductor regions for each of the n slices, and $\mathbf{i} = [i_1 \dots i_m]^T$ contains the currents flowing in the m parallel litz-wire conductors, which are common to all slices. $\mathbf{U} = [U \dots U]^T$ contains the equal supply voltages U over the m parallel conductors. \mathbf{S} and \mathbf{T} are block matrices formed of the stiffness and damping matrices of the slices, matrix \mathbf{D}_Ω maps the conductor potential differences into sources of the field problem and matrix \mathbf{C}_Ω maps the nodal values of the vector potential to the flux linkages of the conductors in each slice. Matrix \mathbf{R} contains the resistances of the conductors in each slice, and matrix \mathbf{M} associates the currents into the correct conductor domains. Matrices \mathbf{D}_Γ and \mathbf{C}_Γ are related to the coupling of the axial and radial slices as explained in [22]. In brief, \mathbf{D}_Γ is a vertical assembly of matrices:

$$\mathbf{D}_{\Gamma, \ell} = \frac{N}{2\pi r_\ell} \left(\int_{\Gamma_{\text{rad}, \ell}} \mathbf{w} d\Gamma \right) \overbrace{\begin{bmatrix} 1 & \dots & 1 \end{bmatrix}}^m \quad (10)$$

which set Neumann boundary conditions on the top and bottom of the core in radial slices based on the total current flowing through the toroid. \mathbf{C}_Γ is a horizontal assembly of matrices:

$$\mathbf{C}_{\Gamma, \ell} = \frac{-l_\ell}{2\pi r_\ell} \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ \vdots \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \left(\int_{\Gamma_{\text{rad}, \ell}} \mathbf{w} d\Gamma \right)^T \quad (11)$$

FIGURE 5 Studied inductors with different wire configuration

which correct the voltage equations based on the flux passing to the core from the radial slices. \boldsymbol{w} is a column vector of shape functions corresponding to the core boundary $\Gamma_{\text{rad},k}$ in the radial slice k with a radial position r_{k^*} .

2.4 | Modelled cases

All simulations are carried out in the frequency domain for computing the AC resistance factor

$$F_R = \frac{R_{\text{ac}}}{R_{\text{dc}}} \quad (12)$$

where R_{ac} and R_{dc} are the AC and DC resistances of the litz wire winding, respectively. R_{ac} is computed by dividing the supply voltage by the total current solved from Equation (9) as:

$$R_{\text{ac}} = \frac{U}{\sum_{j=1}^m i_j} \quad (13)$$

The computation for the winding with three (3×0.6 mm) and four strands (4×0.52 mm) are carried out for three twisting cases. In the first case of each winding, no twisting (0tw) is considered, which is followed by simulations of two cases with three (3tw) and six (6tw) twists per turn in the inductor windings. The wires with 3×0.6 mm and 4×0.52 mm dimensions have L1 twisting configurations.

For the next sets of analysis, different numbers of strands and twisting configurations (levels) are modelled. As shown in the extreme left of Figure 5, two air-core toroids with the windings formed from 105×0.2 mm and 75×0.2 mm wires are analysed. In the air-cores inductors, the windings are wound on PVC toroids. The winding wires for both models have an L2 wire twisting configuration. For the first case, a 7×15 structure is used, meaning that 15 strands are twisted together to form an L1 wire bundle and 7 such bundles are twisted

TABLE 2 Mesh data for the studied cases

Number of strands	Configuration	Number of mesh elements	
		MASM (2D)	3D
3	3×0.6 mm	139,108	718,138
4	4×0.52 mm	140,452	934,592
105	$7 \times 15 \times 0.2$ mm	231,998	–
75	$3 \times 25 \times 0.2$ mm	165,164	–
125	125×0.1 mm	240,588	–
125	$5 \times 25 \times 0.1$ mm	289,560	–
125	$5 \times 5 \times 5 \times 0.1$ mm	319,170	–

to get the final bundle. Similarly, in the second case, a 3×25 structure is constructed. The twisting pitch length for the strands and the L1 wire bundle in the above two cases are: 7×15 : $\tau_1 = 29$ mm; $\tau_2 = 37$ mm and 3×25 : $\tau_1 = 27$ mm; $\tau_2 = 52$ mm.

The last set of cases are modelled for the different litz wire configurations with a 125×0.1 mm wire. The three twisting configurations modelled are 1×125 , 5×25 and $5 \times 5 \times 5$. In each case, both air-core and SMC-core inductors are studied as shown in Figure 5. The twisting configurations for the winding wires are similar to the ones explained in [2]. In the case of 1×125 , all strands are twisted together to form an L1 wire. For 5×25 , 25 strands are twisted to form an L1 wire bundle and five L1 wire bundles are twisted together to get the final L2 wire. The wire with $5 \times 5 \times 5$ configuration has three levels of twisting. Here, five L1 wire bundles, with each consisting of five twisted strands, are twisted together to form a final L2 wire. Five such L2 wire bundles are then twisted together to get the final L3 wire. The pitch lengths for the three cases are: 1×125 : $\tau_1 = 37$ mm, 5×25 : $\tau_1 = 35$ mm; $\tau_2 = 52$ mm, and $5 \times 5 \times 5$: $\tau_1 = 35$ mm; $\tau_2 = 46$ mm; $\tau_3 = 53$ mm. The mesh data for each case is shown in Table 2.

2.5 | 3D model

A 3-D symmetry sector shown in Figure 2 is simulated using COMSOL Multiphysics FEM tool. The 3D FEM model utilizes magnetic and electric field (MEF) interface in the tool to apply the AV formulation. The external current source is set by applying voltage. The following equations are solved using MEF in quasi-static form:

$$\mathbf{B} = \nabla \times \mathbf{A} \quad (14)$$

$$\mathbf{E} = -\nabla V - j\omega \mathbf{A} \quad (15)$$

In the air and the core regions, the electrical conductivity is considered to be zero and thus:

$$\nabla \times \left(\frac{\nabla \times \mathbf{A}}{\mu_r \mu_0} \right) = 0 \quad (16)$$

In the coil region the current density is calculated using:

$$\sigma j\omega \mathbf{A} + \nabla \times \left(\frac{\nabla \times \mathbf{A}}{\mu_0} \right) + \sigma \nabla V = 0 \quad (17)$$

where V is the scalar potential and σ is the electrical conductivity of copper. The Galerkin method is used for discretizing the above equations to solve the FEM problem. The periodic boundary conditions are applied on the sides of the symmetry sector model. The 3D FEM was only possible for the cases with 3×0.6 mm and 4×0.52 mm wires. Based on the mesh data in Table 2, the required 3D discretization for other cases with higher number of strands would result into an extremely large problem. It would have been impossible to solve problem in 3D with available computational resources.

3 | RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The computational results for the MASM are simulated on a single Windows computer with 32 GB RAM and Intel Core i7-8650U (4 cores 8 threads) 1.9 GHz processor. The validation of MASM results is carried using 3D FEM and experimental measurements. The 3D FEM was carried out using COMSOL Multiphysics tool for cases where 3D FEM was possible within available computational resources. All 3D FEM simulations were carried out in 64 GB, Intel Core i7-3930K (6 cores 12 threads) 3.2 GHz processor. Both the MASM and 3D FEM are used for computing the AC resistance factor for 1 kHz–1 MHz frequency range. The cases, in which 3D computation were not possible, the validations for MASM results are made through measurements. All the computed cases from Table 1. are shown in the subsequent sections with detailed discussion.

FIGURE 6 AC resistance factor (a) 3×0.6 mm strands and (b) 4×0.52 mm strand cases

3.1 | Comparison to 3D model

Figure 6 shows the comparison of results computed from MASM and 3D simulations. In Figure 6a, F_R is computed for three different twisting pitch lengths in the air-core inductor winding with 3×0.6 mm wire. A similar set of results is computed for the 4×0.52 mm wire winding with the air-core in Figure 6b. From both results, we can observe that the influence of the proximity effect on the winding resistance is prominent after 150 kHz. However, the untwisted (0tw) case has lower effect of proximity on the winding resistance after 150 kHz. The results of MASM and 3D simulations are reasonably close.

3.2 | Proximity effect

To understand more about proximity effect, litz wire cases with level-2 twisting schemes were analysed for 105×0.2 mm and 75×0.2 mm wires. With such high number of strands, it was impossible to use 3D FEM approach for validation with the available computational resources. Hence, experimental results were used for authenticating the MASM computations. The computational and measurement results for air-core inductor winding using 105×0.2 mm and 75×0.2 mm wires, are shown in Figure 7. The motive of selecting the above two cases

FIGURE 7 AC resistance factor for 105×0.2 mm and 75×0.2 mm from MASM and measurements

was to authenticate the MASM computation for different wire dimensions and see the impact of inter-bundle proximity effect when same twisting schemes are used. It can easily be seen how increasing the number of strands affects the winding resistance under proximity effect. Hence, a correct selection of the configuration along with the number of strands and bundles becomes vital for optimal operation of inductors at high frequency. The measurements in Figure 7 were carried out using a GW Instek 8101G LCR meter. The measurements have lot of disturbances due to the limitations with the measurement resolution for low values of resistances. Nevertheless, the measured values from both cases are in the same ranges as the computations. The error bars in the graph were obtained by performing 100 measurements for each case.

High measurement uncertainties were clearly visible for the mid-range of frequencies, where the resistance of the winding is low. Such uncertainties have also been observed in measurements of winding resistance for two winding device studied in [26]. Note that the logarithmic vertical axis scale in the plot also causes the uncertainties to appear relatively bigger at the lower end of the vertical range.

3.3 | Effect of twisting on winding resistance

In Figure 8, a realistic case of litz wire windings from 125×0.1 mm wires are modelled and measured for the air-core inductor cases. In order to investigate the impact of twisting schemes on the AC winding resistance factor, three possible twisting schemes are computed and shown in Figure 8. It is clearly visible from the graph that for the L1 wire (1×125), the proximity effect starts influencing after 110 kHz. This has also been referred as intra-bundle skin effect in [5]. In the case of the L2 wire, this phenomenon is slightly delayed. However, it starts following the trajectory of the L1 after 900 kHz. By adopting the L3 wire ($5 \times 5 \times 5$), the impact of bundle level skin and the inter-bundle proximity effects can be suppressed after 200 kHz. The measurements performed to validate the computational results are shown in the same figure for all three configurations. The computational results are compared against the measurements from inductors with the same configuration. Again, 100

FIGURE 8 AC resistance factor for 125×0.1 mm with L1, L2, and L3 wires from MASM and measurements

measurements for each case were recorded and error bars were plotted to see the relative behaviour of F_R . The values obtained from the measurements were close to the ones computed using MASM. Below 100 kHz, large variations in the measurements prevent accurate comparison of the simulated and the measured results. Above 100 kHz, the simulated values are lower than the measured ones. However, the overall variation for all three cases is captured by the simulation model. One of the possibilities for such discrepancy could be the manufacturing tolerances of the litz wire itself as well as the winding. For example, in the hand-wound toroid, the turns are not exactly equally distributed, but the spacing between turns varies. The instrument readings also show quite high variations among the repeated 100 measurements for each frequency. The simulated values differ from the averaged values of the measurements relatively more in the mid-range of frequency from 100 to 800 kHz for all three cases. However, at other frequencies, the simulations match well with the measurements. The frequency dependency of the resistance is a result of inhomogeneous current density distribution. Hence, to see the effect of different twisting configurations on the current density distribution in both sets of cases, the relative deviation of the local RMS current density from the RMS of the spatially averaged current density was computed and is shown in Figure 9. This also illustrates the relative differences in the magnitudes of the branch currents. Figure 9a shows the effect of adding more bundles on current density distribution. The middle bundle for the 105×0.2 mm wire carries the least amount of current in the high frequency range under the proximity effect between the bundles. On the other hand, 75×0.2 mm wire has relatively less influence of proximity effect due to the smaller number of strands and bundles. This scenario can be observed over the entire frequency range after 20 kHz in Figure 7. In the case of the 125×0.1 mm wires (Figure 9b), the L1 and L2 wires show proximity effect between strands and bundles, respectively. The current density in the middle section of both wires is low. The L3 wire provides a good possibility to suppress the inter-bundle proximity effect with multiple levels of twisting for higher frequencies. However, considering the cost aspects, the L3 wire will be more expensive. Hence, the L2 wire becomes an ideal choice here for the given dimensions. Similar results are also observed in [2] with a different strand diameter.

FIGURE 9 Relative deviation of the local RMS current density from the RMS of the spatially averaged current density in the wires at 100 kHz (a) 105×0.2 mm and 75×0.2 (from left) and (b) 125×0.1 mm (from left): L1, L2, and L3 wires

FIGURE 10 Comparison of SMC-core inductor impedance modelled in MASM against measured values for 125×0.1 mm wire under all twisting schemes: (a) L1 (1×125) wire, (b) L2 (5×25) wire and (c) L3 ($5 \times 5 \times 5$) wire

3.4 | Effect of core on winding resistance under different twisting configurations

To analyse the impact of core on the small-signal behaviour of the inductor windings, impedances for all three configurations of the 125×0.1 mm wire were modelled using MASM and validated against measurements in Figure 10. The obtained real and imaginary parts of impedances for all three cases are quite similar and show good agreement with the measurements. In Figure 11, the winding resistances are extracted from the computations, and the calculated winding resistance factors F_R are compared against the air-core inductor cases

for the same twisting configurations in Figure 8a. Based on the results, it can be understood that the selected SMC-core of same dimension has no impact on the small-signal winding resistance. Such study of winding resistance for highly complex structure like litz wire winding would not be possible with the 3D FEM modelling approach considering the limitations of computational resources. The experimental approach also imposes uncertainties due to limitations of the measurement instrument [26]. Hence, MASM opens a possibility here to make rapid computations for different twisting configurations and strands within reasonable accuracy ranges.

FIGURE 11 Simulated AC resistance factor of winding for 125×0.1 mm with L1, L2 and L3 wires

FIGURE 13 Simulation time for 125×0.1 mm, 105×0.2 mm, and 75×0.2 mm cases

FIGURE 12 Speedup ratio for 3×0.6 mm and 4×0.52 mm cases

3.5 | Computational time

For the computed cases the simulation times were comparatively observed. In the case of 3×0.6 mm and 4×0.52 mm wires the speedup ratios for MASM over 3D computations were recorded from 1 kHz to 1 MHz, which are shown in Figure 12. Based on the obtained data, the MASM computations are significantly faster than the 3D computations with COMSOL Multiphysics. On an average scale over the studied frequency range, MASM is 101 and 83 times faster for the 3×0.6 mm and 4×0.52 mm cases, respectively. The average times taken by the 3×0.6 mm and 4×0.52 mm MASM simulations were 5.5 and 6.8 s per frequency. The same cases took 458 and 693 s per frequency, respectively with 3D computations. The major benefits of MASM were observed with the 105×0.2 mm, 75×0.2 mm, and 125×0.1 mm wires, which are more realistic cases of litz wire. The simulation times for those cases are shown in the Figure 13. The 105 case took about 14.8 s on an average scale, while the 75 case took 7.6 s. The simulation times for all the three cases of the 125×0.1 mm wire were averaged and they are plotted in the same graph. From the graph, over the studied frequency range, the average simulation time for the 125×0.1 mm wire was 14.9 s. It should be noted that the 3-D computations were carried out in a system with higher computational resources. On the other hand, MASM computations were performed on a system with less computational resources.

4 | CONCLUSION

An approach of modelling toroidal litz wire windings by using a multiaxial sliced finite element model was shown with a detailed study of multiple litz wire configurations. The influence of twisting schemes and twisting pitch on the AC resistance factor for toroidal inductor winding was analysed. The effect of core on the winding resistance was also studied using the same model. The model enables to carry out computations of complex litz wire structures which are not possible in 3D. This can significantly reduce the time required in design optimization processes for magnetic components.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors have no conflict of interest to disclose.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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